

SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC AND CONDUCTOMETRIC STUDIES OF METAL COMPLEXES OF 3-HYDROXY-1-*p*-SULPHONATOPHENYL-3-PHENYL-TRIAZINE. PART I. PALLADIUM COMPLEX

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Palladium forms an intensely yellow-coloured, water-soluble complex with 3-hydroxy-1-*p*-sulphonatophenyl-3-phenyltriazine. The formula of the complex, established spectrophotometrically, by applying Job's method, slope ratio method and molar ratio method and also conductometrically, has been determined to be PdR₂ (R=reagent). The molecular extinction coefficient has been found to be 18.75×10^3 at 425m μ . The dissociation constant at 25° has been found to be 3×10^{-11} and free energy of formation of the complex is -15.72Kcal./mole.

Recently Sogani and Bhattacharyya (*Anal. Chem.*, 1957, 29, 397) have reported the use of 3-hydroxy-1-*p*-sulphonatophenyl-3-phenyltriazine as an excellent colorimetric reagent for palladium. The reagent and the metal complexes given by it are water-soluble. The colour development with palladium is almost instantaneous and the intensity remains unaltered even after 24 hours. The system is stable under wide ranges of *p*_H and temperature variation. The reagent and the palladium complex have well-separated absorption peaks so that the excess of the reagent does not interfere in the photometric estimations.

The present investigation was undertaken with a view to establishing the formula of palladium-3-hydroxy-1-*p*-sulphonatophenyl-3-phenyltriazine complex, using spectrophotometric and conductometric methods. In spectrophotometric method, we have adopted Job's method of continued variation (*Compt. rend.*, 1928, 180, 928; *Ann. chim.*, 1928, x, 9, 113), slope ratio method (Harvey and Manning, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 4488) and molar ratio method (Yoe and Jones, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Anal. Ed.*, 1944, 15, 111). The empirical formula has been found to be PdR₂. This has been verified conductometrically. The chelate structure may be represented as:

The dissociation constant, and hence, the stability constant, the free energy of formation of the palladium complex and molecular extinction coefficient have been determined.

EXPERIMENTAL

3-Hydroxy-1-*p*-sulphonatophenyl-3-phenyltriazine was prepared, by the method given by Sogani and Bhattacharyya (*loc. cit.*). The reagent solution used for spectrophotometric work was $M \times 10^{-4}$ and for conductometric work, $M \times 10^{-3}$ solution.

Standard palladium chloride solution was prepared by dissolving approximately 0.5 g. of analytically pure palladium chloride in a small amount of HCl (dil.)

and making up the volume to 500 c.c. The palladium content of this solution was determined by precipitating it with dimethylglyoxime. It was further diluted to give $M \times 10^{-3}$ for conductometric measurements and $M \times 10^{-4}$ for spectrophotometric work.

10% HCl (v/v) and 10% sodium acetate (w/v) were used for adjusting the p_H of the solutions between 3.0 and 3.2 in the spectrophotometric work.

All absorption measurements were made with a Bausch & Lomb 'Spectronic -20' colorimeter, using 1 cm cuvette. A Beckman glass electrode p_H -meter (model H-2) was used for all p_H measurements. For conductivity measurements, a Kohlrausch Universal bridge was used. An 'Advance' A. F. generator (model H-1) was used as a source of alternating current.

Nature of the Complex formed.—In a set of experiments, mixtures containing varying proportions of palladium : reagent (*i.e.* 1:1, 1:2, 1:3 etc.) were prepared and the optical densities at different wave-lengths in each case measured. In all the cases, the maximum absorption occurred at 415 $m\mu$, thus indicating formation of only one complex with the reagent (Vosburgh and Cooper, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 63, 437).

Composition of the Complex

The unolar composition of the palladium complex was investigated by the following methods.

Job's Method.—For studying the formula of the complex by this method, the palladium content in the final solutions was varied between $2 \times 10^{-6} M$ and $18 \times 10^{-6} M$ and the p_H was kept at about 3.0. Absorption was measured at 415, 425 and 430 $m\mu$. Fig. 1 shows the curves obtained by applying this method. The maxima at 0.67 indicate PdR_2 as the formula of the complex.

FIG. 1

Slope Ratio Method.—The concentration of the variable component was varied from $1 \times 10^{-3} M$ to $10 \times 10^{-5} M$ in presence of excess concentration of $8 \times 10^{-4} M$ of the constant component. The p_H of the solution was kept at about 3.0. Fig. 2 records the measured optical density at $425 m\mu$, plotted against the concentration of the variable component. The slopes of the two straight lines give palladium to reagent ratio as 1:2, which is quite in conformity with the previous method.

FIG. 2

Upper curve showing Pd varying and the lower one, the reagent varying. Conc. of the const. component = $8 \times 10^{-5} M$. $p_H = 2.8-3$. $425 m\mu$.

Molar Ratio Method.—A series of solutions, in which the molar ratio of palladium to reagent varied from 1:0.5 to 1:10, was prepared and their absorption was measured at $425 m\mu$. The lower curve (a) in Fig. 3 does not show any sharp break owing to the dissociation of the complex in dilute solutions. By adding 5 c.c. of $M \times 10^{-3}$ -KCl solution to suppress the dissociation of the complex, a method recommended by Harvey and Manning (*loc. cit.*), a sharp break is obtained (Fig. 3, upper curve 'b') at a ratio of 2 moles of reagent to 1 mole of palladium.

Fig. 3

Conductivity Method.— $M \times 10^{-3}$ -Palladium chloride (6 c.c.) solution was taken in a conductivity cell and its conductivity was measured. Equimolecular reagent solution was added from a burette. The observed conductivity was corrected for volume. Fig. 4 shows the conductivity values plotted against c.c. of the reagent added. The break in the curve at 12 c.c. of the reagent solution indicates PdR_3 as the formula of the complex. This is in agreement with the spectrophotometric results.

FIG. 4

DISCUSSION

The dissociation of the complex can be written as :

where C is the total concentration of the complex in moles per litre assuming no dissociation and α is the degree of dissociation. The equilibrium constant K is given by the equation :

$$K = \frac{\alpha C \times (2\alpha C)^2}{C(1-\alpha)} = \frac{4\alpha^3 C^2}{1-\alpha}$$

The value of α may be obtained from the upper curve (a) in Fig. 3 by the following relationship

$$\alpha = (E_m - E_s)/E_m$$

where E_m is the maximum absorption obtained from the horizontal portion of the curve, when all the palladium is present in the form of the complex and E_s is the observed absorption of the stoichiometric molar ratio of the reagent to palladium in the complex. The value of α at room temperature (25°) on calculation comes to 0.25. The concentration ' C ' of the complex is the same as the total concentration of palladium, which is $6 \times 10^{-6} M$. The value of K at 25° is equal to 3×10^{-12} . The stability constant K' of the complex is the reciprocal of the dissociation constant and is equal to 3.33×10^{11} .

The standard free energy of formation of the complex from palladium chloride and 3-hydroxy-1-*p*-sulphonatophenyl-3-phenyltriazine is calculated from the relation,

$$\Delta F^\circ = RT \ln K,$$

where the terms have their usual significance. In this system the value of ΔF° works out to be -15.72 Kcal./mole at 25° . The reaction is accompanied with a considerable decrease of free energy at room temperature, indicating the spontaneous nature of the reaction.

Molecular extinction coefficient (ϵ) is equal to the slope of straight line 'a' in Fig. 2.

$$\epsilon = \text{slope (a)} = 1875 \times 10^3.$$

The authors express their gratitude to Principal Bhim Sen for providing facilities in the College. They are thankful to Dr. S. C. Bhattacharyya, Asstt. Director, National Chemical Laboratory, Poona, for taking keen interest in the present work.